

DOUBLE NOTCHED SPLIT CANTILEVER TEST METHOD TO MEASURE MIXED MODE II AND III INTERLAMINAR TOUGHNESS

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SUMMARY

A novel test method to evaluate mixed mode II and III interlaminar fracture toughness is proposed, where numerical method such as finite element analysis is crucial. The test method may be said a modified split cantilever test. The twisting force existing in the case of the simple split cantilever test was avoided by making specimen symmetric by introducing two delaminations. The two cracks stably and self-similarly grew with the increase of the applied displacement. The energy release rate was numerically determined from the experimentally obtained data such as the load, applied displacement and the experimentally measured crack configuration by using finite element method. A wide range of mixed mode critical energy release rate can be roughly obtained by one test trial. The method can be conveniently used to estimate mode II and III mixed mode interlaminar fracture toughness.

Keywords: Delamination, Mixed mode interlaminar fracture toughness, Experiment, Finite element method

1. INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites are used particularly for aerospace structures due to their high specific strength and stiffness. However, the laminated composite structures subjected to static, impact and/or cyclic loads may have significant interlaminar damage owing to its insufficient interlaminar toughness. So, the interlaminar fracture toughness is regarded as an important index of the failure tolerance of the laminates. Considering that not only interlaminar normal (mode I) but also inplane shear (mode II) and out-of-plane shear (mode III) stress field contributes delamination propagation, the values of all three individual and/or mixed interlaminar toughness must be evaluated to fully characterize the interlaminar fracture property of the composite laminates with using appropriate test methods.

There have been numerous studies concerning a test method to measure interlaminar fracture toughness owing to its importance. The mode I fracture toughness of the laminated composites is well measured by DCB (Double Cantilever Beam) test method [1-5]. The mode II fracture toughness of the laminated composite is also obtained through comparatively simple ENF (End Notched Flexure) test method [1, 5, 6]. Mixed normal and inplane shear (mode I and II) fracture test can be also conducted through MMB (Mixed Mode Bending) and CLS (Cracked Lap Shear) test method [1, 2]. Though experimental techniques for measuring mode III including Edge Crack Torsion (ECT) test method are proposed by several workers [7-10], they are not so

handy as those proposed for measuring mode I and II fracture toughnesses. Donaldson [11] proposed the SCB(Split Cantilever Bending) test method. Yoshikawa et al. [12]proposed an interesting test method by introducing two cracks to measure mode III fracture toughness.

Szekrenyes [13] and de Morais et al.[14] have recently proposed interesting test methods to measure mixed mode II and III fracture toughness, respectively, whose concepts were superposition of ENF/SCB and ENF/ECT test, respectively. The test methods somehow realized failure due to mixed mode II and III condition, but accurate determination of the mixed mode were not easy owing to non-uniform stress condition for both methods. Test methods to measure mixed mode I and III and those of all component fracture toughness have not been proposed yet as long as our knowledge.

In the split cantilever bending test method, both Mode II and Mode III components exist at its crack front at the initial state and during stable crack growth. In the present study, we will propose a modified SCB test method easy to conduct and possible to evaluate wide range of mixed mode II and III fracture toughness by a single test by using finite element technique due to its nonuniform mixed mode fracture condition.

2. EXPERIMENT

2.1 Theoretical assessment

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of the present test method a glued specimen with homogeneous and isotropic interface was made instead of the real composite materials. The specimen configuration is shown in Figure 1(a). Two cracks are introduced so that the specimen is symmetric about center plane. The inside part of the cracked specimen is twice as thick as the both outside portions. The center cracked portion of the specimen is vertically loaded and the both side portions are simply-supported. The specimen bends without twisting owing to its symmetry and bending stress σ_x and shear stress τ_{xy} occur in the cross sections of the cracked portions of the specimen as shown in Figure 1(b). Stresses of same magnitude and opposite sign occur at the corresponding point in the other cracked portion. Normal stress σ and shear stress τ on the inclined surface normal to the cracked surface and parallel to the crack edge cause mainly mode II and mode III components, respectively. The curved crack front tended to grow self-similarly and stably with the increase of the applied displacement, which is quite convenient feature of the present method to conduct the failure experiment like the DCB test method. The average critical total energy release rate, of course, can be obtained by the area method as the DCB test method. It is thought to be mode III dominant considering the stress condition for the inclined crack, which will be shown later from the result of the finite element analysis. The energy release rate distribution along the crack front satisfies the critical condition during stable crack growth. The mixed mode II and III fracture toughness can be determined, if the energy release rate distribution is obtained along the crack front by using appropriate way such as finite element method. In order to obtain the mixed mode fracture toughness, the crack shape and applied displacement or the applied load are necessary after knowing the elastic properties of the specimen.

Figure 1 Schematic figure of double-notched split cantilever beam test (a). Expected internal forces and the mechanism of mixed mode fracture stress field at the inclined crack front.(b).

2.2 Test Fixture and specimen

A test fixture for the present test is shown in Figure 2. Two horizontal round pins support the bottom surface of the outer-ports of the specimen. The pins being sufficiently stiff can slide in the block to adjust for specimen thickness. A vertical bar with round head applies downward displacement to the center portion of the specimen. A ball bearing fixed in the outer frame supports the vertical bar in order to prevent it from tilting.

Specimens were prepared by gluing three acrylic plates by an epoxy adhesive agent (Figure 3) to demonstrate the feasibility of the present method. The center plate was twice as thick as the rests. PTFE films (20 μm thick) were placed at both end portions of the plates to make the adhesive as uniform as possible and to introduce starter cracks. The specimens were cut out from the glued plate and machined to specified dimensions. Acrylic resin plate was selected in order to easily observe the shape of the both crack

fronts with naked eyes. The dimensions of the specimen are given in Figure 3. Natural cracks were introduced a little by mode I loading condition before the tests. The length and the thickness of the cracked portions must be carefully determined in order not to yield or buckle during the test.

The cross-head speed was set 0.25 mm/min. The crack propagation was recorded through digital video camera. The crack shapes were measured and determined through the video camera images after the test.

Figure 2 Fixture for the double notched split cantilever test.

Figure 3 Specimen and its dimensions. The total thickness of the specimen was 20 mm.

A relationship between the applied load and the movement of the cross head is plotted in Figure 4. The crack shapes were shown in Figure 5. The numbers of the figures mean the corresponding loading indicated in Figure 4. The crack growth initiated from the edge of the originally straight crack at the load of the point 1 in Figure 4. With the increase of the applied displacement the crack spread to the whole width of the specimen from the both sides as seen in the second picture of Figure 5. Then, the applied load started decreasing with the applied displacement which was caused by the decrease of the stiffness of the specimen due to the whole crack propagation. The continuous curve means that the crack stably grew without any unstable crack propagation. The critical condition of the crack propagation was attained at all the points along the curved crack front. The two cracks were almost symmetric with the neutral axis of the specimen. The crack shapes were maintained during crack propagation as shown in photographs (2-5) in Figure 5. The sizes of the two cracks tended to be equal but some difference existed because of the difference of the

toughness of the interfaces probably due to nonuniform adhesive thickness and quality. The difference of the lengths of the two cracks was not serious problem for specifying the toughness if the necessary conditions, the two crack shapes and the applied load (or applied displacement) were measured.

Figure 4 Load-displacement curve for an glued specimen.

Figure 5 Profiles of crack fronts in an adhesively glued interface of acrylic resin specimen observed during the test.

3. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analyses (ABAQUS 6.61) were conducted to evaluate the energy release rate distribution along crack front of the measured crack shape and the applied load. A finite element model is shown in Figure 6. A half of the specimen was analyzed with eight-noded brick element C3D8 considering its symmetry condition. The region near the crack front was discretized by finer mesh to obtain accurate result. Material properties used in the analyses were determined by referring the catalog values. Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν of the acrylic resin used in the analysis are 2.9 GPa and 0.39, respectively. The energy release rate was calculated with the virtual crack closure technique.

Figure 6 Finite element mesh and boundary conditions

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The energy release rate distribution for the case of straight crack ($c=50$ mm, $\delta=2$ mm) is plotted against the position in the height direction of the initial straight crack in Figure 7. The mode I component was negligible as expected. The mode II component relating to the bending stress was large near the edges. The mode III component relating to the transverse shear stress was thought to be maximum at the neutral axis. The Poisson ratio effect, however, caused large mode III component near the side edges. The mode III component was also maximum at the edge for the specimen of this dimensions. The energy release rate was large near the side of the specimen where the crack started growing in the test as observed in the photograph 1 and 2 of Figure 5.

The crack propagation was simulated using cohesive element assuming $G_{IIc}=G_{IIIc}$. The failure process was successfully simulated as shown in Figure 8. The crack growth history was quite similar to the experiment (Figure 5). When $G_{IIc}<G_{IIIc}$, the crack where more mode II component is included will propagate faster than present simulation. So, crack is longer near the side and the inclination of the crack will be larger than the result of Figure 8. When $G_{IIc}>G_{IIIc}$, the inclination will be less.

The energy release rate distributions at the stages 2 and 4 (Figure 4) are plotted against the normalized position of the interface in Figures 9 and 10 with the crack shapes. The distribution of the mode components are perfectly different from the straight crack (Figure 7). Mode II component, being zero at the center of the crack front,

increased with the distance from the center line of the beam. On the other hand, Mode III component being maximum at the center point decreased basically with the distance from the neutral axis. The mode II component is almost zero in the wide area near the center portion. The mode III component tended to decrease with the distance from the center line in spite that mode II component is nearly zero. The reason is not clear yet. The energy release rate tended to be large near the side edges probably due to the edge effect. The mode ratio is dependent on the measured profile of the crack. The measurement of the crack profile must be carefully done to avoid the inaccuracy of the results.

Figure 7 Energy release rate distribution at the initial straight crack when applied displacement was $P=40N$, $c=40$ mm.

Figure 8 Crack propagation history numerically obtained by using a cohesive element when $G_{IIc}=G_{IIIc}$.

Figure 9 Total and each energy release rate distribution along the crack front when the applied displacement is 0.65 mm

Figure 10 Total and each energy release rate distribution along the crack front when the applied displacement was 1.71 mm

The mixed mode II and III fracture toughness is plotted in Figure 11. The data near the edge were omitted from the figure to avoid the inaccurate results owing to the edge effect. The horizontal axis is mode II component and the vertical axis shows the mode III component. The critical energies of mode II and mode III components seems to be similar in the present specimen. The fracture criterion for mixed mode condition (mode II and mode III) can be determined from the present figure.

Figure 11 Variation of mixed mode ratio of critical energy release rate

5. CONCLUSIONS

A novel test method, which we called double-notched split cantilever beam test, was proposed to evaluate mixed mode II and III fracture toughness. Experimental and finite element studies were demonstrated to show the applicability of the present method. We showed that the crack stably and self-similarly grew with the increase of the applied displacement and formed a curved crack front along which critical condition was achieved. The finite element analyses were suitable to evaluate the critical energy release rate along the crack front. It could provide a useful test method for the evaluation of the mixed mode II and III fracture toughness.

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